

Preprint: Redistributive Preferences and the Contact Hypothesis: Assessing how Emotions towards Economic Inequality are Affected by Loose and Socio-Economically Diverse Contacts and Impinge on Public Policy Preferences

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Abstract

In this paper, we aim to test the implications of the renowned 'contact hypothesis', developed by Gordon Allport in the 1950s, in the realm of economic inequality research. More specifically, we focus on whether the frequency of being 'exposed', when out and about, to people of socio-economically different backgrounds, i.e. either poorer or richer, than oneself is significantly associated with attitudes and emotions towards economic inequality. Preliminary linear regression analyses, based on representative online survey data from Great Britain and France, suggest, that loose contacts with people poorer than oneself in both countries strongly affect inequality-related emotions as different as compassion, frustration, anger, indifference, moral outrage or sadness. Being 'exposed' to richer people than oneself, by contrast, seems to impede more intensive emotional responses to a set of different stimuli of economic inequality. Similarly, we find that more frequent contacts are directly associated with redistributive preferences. In the next analytical step, to be presented at IPSA 2025, we aim to investigate the underlying causal mechanisms that seem to connect these contacts with inequality perceptions, emotions and redistributive preferences.

Introduction

Background and Relevance

A well-established body of research shows that intergroup dynamics in local contexts, such as residential areas, public spaces, and neighbourhoods, play a critical role in shaping individuals' attitudes and behaviours (Nathan & Sands, 2023). A substantial portion of this scholarship is rooted in the foundational work of Allport (1954) and his social psychological exploration of the "contact hypothesis". Nevertheless, some challenges in synthesising findings across this field stem from insufficient attention to how mechanisms may vary across political systems and from overlooking alternative frameworks beyond traditional social and political psychology (Nathan & Sands, 2023).

In this vein, in recent years, empirical research in political science has broadened studies on the *contact theory* by increasingly examining the influence of intergroup contact on political behaviour (Nathan & Sands, 2023). In this effort, while the psychology literature has primarily

focused on understanding the roots of intergroup prejudice (Allport, 1954; Pettigrew & Tropp, 2006; Levy Paluck et al., 2019), political science research has been more concerned with how these intergroup dynamics influence political attitudes and behaviour (e.g., Beber et al., 2014; Glaser, 2003; Jardina, 2021).

Extending its application beyond racial and ethnic divisions, scholars have started to test the contact hypothesis with individuals of varying socioeconomic status whose studies show how everyday exposure to individuals from different socioeconomic backgrounds in public spaces, workplaces, or transit systems can shape perceptions of inequality and attitudes toward redistributive policies (Sands & de Kadt, 2020). This development includes not only direct or meaningful interactions but also more incidental or diffuse exposure, sometimes referred to as *loose contact* (Enos, 2017). However, the incorporation of class-based intergroup relationships in the field remains limited, and further research in this direction is needed (Cote et al., 2017; Dixon et al., 2020).

In this paper, we draw on insights from political science regarding political behaviour, while also examining the psychological mechanisms that may underlie the effects of class-based contact on political action. In this sense, we focus on emotions as an intermediary mechanism through which the experience of contact with poorer or richer individuals is translated into changes in political attitudes.

The Contact Hypothesis and class-based intergroup dynamics

The contact hypothesis, originally formulated by Allport (1954) in his seminal work *The Nature of Prejudice*, posits that interpersonal contact between members of different social groups can reduce prejudice and negative attitudes. This theory has been central to research on intergroup relations, discrimination, and social cohesion, and has informed a wide range of political and educational interventions over the past fifty years (Pettigrew & Tropp, 2006). Thus, the contact hypothesis has been extended beyond its original scope and has explored intergroup dynamics across diverse social contexts, cultural settings and also considering different social groups (Pettigrew & Tropp, 2006; Levy Paluck et al., 2019).

From another but related field, recent studies suggest that notions of inequality and wealth distribution are systematically shaped by the structure of the environment—in particular, by the distribution of wealth itself (Dawtry, Sutton, & Sibley, 2015, 2019; Galesic, Olsson, & Rieskamp, 2012, 2018). The characteristics of the local environments in which individuals live or work—the physical context—may provide cues about economic inequality. Sands and de Kadt (2020) follow this approach: using a placebo-controlled field experiment in South African neighbourhoods, they examined how local exposure to inequality influences support for redistribution among individuals of low socioeconomic status. The experiment involved randomly placing a high-status luxury car—a real-world symbol of economic disparity—in public spaces. Pedestrians were then invited to sign a petition advocating higher taxation on the wealthy to promote redistribution. The presence of the high-status vehicle increased the likelihood of signing the petition, even after accounting for placebo effects. In line with this, Bailey (2013), using data from the 2009 British Social Attitudes Survey, shows that neighbourhood context shapes attitudes toward redistribution, with knowledge accumulated through local experience likely playing a key role. In particular, support for redistribution tends to be stronger in more deprived neighbourhoods. These findings suggest that everyday signals of social class heighten awareness of economic inequality and can shape redistributive preferences.

While increasing spatial segregation appears to weaken overall support for redistributive policies, such signals of social class are conveyed not only through objects, architecture, and

physical geographies, but also through the social environment—particularly through interactions with members of other social groups. That is, both spatial and social exposure to inequality might shape redistributive preferences. Returning to the contact hypothesis, research shows that contact with upper-class individuals tended to be associated with greater legitimization of inequality (Vargas Salfate & Stern, 2023), while positive interactions with working-class individuals made people more inclined to advocate for their rights (Vázquez et al., 2022). Similarly, drawing on network and contact theories, Newman (2014) shows that having friends who are experiencing financial distress can indirectly increase support for government efforts to reduce inequality. Galesic et al. (2012, 2018) explain this through their social sampling model: The judgments about a particular social attribute –e.g., income inequality– may be based upon relevant instances a person has previously encountered in their immediate social environment. Since one can rarely experience the social attributes in an exhaustive way, the individual recalls a limited number of interactions from which they obtained information about this social attribute. Then, the person extrapolates from these social samples -also a “convenience sample”- to wider society (Dawtry, Sutton, & Sibley, 2015, 2019). In this sense, people may understand income and wealth distribution via their immediate social world (Dawtry et al., 2019).

However, these social interactions are limited and not representative of the wider population. People tend to encounter others who are geographically proximal to them and share relatively similar sociodemographic attributes (e.g., ethnicity, age, education, and socioeconomic status) (Dawtry et al., 2019). It is understood that this is due to a fundamental organizing principle of social networks: homophily. That is, contact between similar people occurs more frequently than contact between dissimilar people (Lazarsfeld & Merton, 1954; Marsden, 1987; McPherson, Smith-Lovin & Cook, 2001; Reagans, 2011). In this sense, in homogeneous communities in terms of socioeconomic status, such as deprived or private and gated neighbourhoods, social interactions are constrained by the lack of opportunities to meet people of different socioeconomic levels.

1.4. Emotional Responses and Political Behaviour

Since the early formulations of contact theory, scholars have argued that intergroup contact reduces prejudice through a range of individual-level psychological processes. Among these, emotional responses—alongside factors such as social trust and stereotypes—play a particularly important role in shaping attitudes and behaviour toward outgroups (Nathan & Sands, 2023).

In particular, emotions might either promote or discourage different responses to reduce poverty and economic inequality. In research on poverty, positive emotions, such as empathy, are associated with helping behaviour (Gonzalez & Lay, 2017; Klebaniuk, 2018; Yúdica et al., 2020; Zucker & Weiner, 1993), civic commitment (Luengo-Kanacri et al., 2016), volunteering and donations (Willer, Wimer & Owens, 2015). Moreover, research in different contexts has found that emotions play a critical role in shaping people's support for policies that address economic inequality or seek to reduce poverty (Thomas & McGarty, 2011; Krauth-Guber & Bonnot, 2020; Landmann & Hess 2016; Hechler & Kessler, 2018; Harth, Kessler & Leach, 2008; Tan, Liu, Zheng & Huang, 2015; Luengo Kanacri et al. 2016). For example, emotions would underpin support for government interventions through different policies involving economic trade-offs, including raising the federal minimum wage and food stamp programs (Hernandez-Ramos et al., 2019). In this paper, we focus on preferences for redistribution as one of the strategies to reduce economic inequality. We understand redistributive preferences as the political process that modifies how resources are allocated across a population (Sznycer et al., 2017). In our framework, redistribution is conceptualized as involving a trade-off between taxation levels and government social spending, where increasing one typically requires adjusting the other.

The question of why individuals support or oppose such redistribution has been linked to underlying psychological mechanisms that shape their reactions to policies—mechanisms that interpret external information and activate emotional and motivational systems, ultimately influencing attitudes toward redistribution (Boyer & Petersen, 2012; Cosmides & Tooby, 2006; Sznycer et al., 2017). In this study, we focus on class-based contact as a form of external information that triggers emotional processes, which in turn shape redistributive preferences.

Among the various emotional responses to economic inequality, anger, moral outrage, and compassion have proven especially influential in shaping attitudes towards redistribution. However, whereas anger directed at disadvantaged groups tends to be linked to lower support for government aid (Gonzalez & Lay, 2017; Klebaniuk, 2018; Yúdica et al., 2020; Zucker & Weiner, 1993), moral outrage emerges as a key predictor of greater support for redistributive policies (Garcia-Castro et al., 2022; Montada & Schneider, 1989; Vezzoli et al., 2022; Wakslak, Jost, Tyler & Chen, 2007). Moral outrage can be understood as an emotional response that arises when people perceive a violation of moral standards, especially those linked to fairness or justice (Batson et al., 2007). Likewise, compassion also emerges as a key emotional driver of support for redistribution. Individuals with higher compassion are more likely to endorse redistributive policies (Yúdica et al., 2021; Gonzalez & Lay, 2017), and this effect is independent of other motives such as envy or self-interest (Sznycer et al., 2017). In contrast, indifference is generally associated with inaction. It is conceptualized by some scholars as a reduced emotional sensitivity toward situations or individuals that would normally evoke an emotional response (Price et al., 2009). Unlike a neutral or emotionally blank state, indifference carries additional interpretive weight because observers expect an emotional reaction to the situation, and its absence prompts specific inferences (Cohen-Chen et al., 2022). Despite its potential relevance, indifference remains relatively understudied compared to other emotional responses.

Our research aims to address the question of how the individual's responses to inequality in terms of redistributive preferences are configured through their social interactions, via emotional experiences around economic inequality. As a first hypothesis (H1), it is expected that individuals who report more frequent contact with poorer people in their daily lives will show stronger negative emotional responses to both income and wealth inequality (such as sadness, anger, moral outrage, and frustration), as well as higher levels of compassion. Similarly, (H2) frequent contact with wealthier individuals is also expected to correlate with negative emotions towards income and wealth inequality. Finally, it is expected that (H3) social contact, either with poor or rich people, influences attitudes toward redistribution both directly and indirectly, through the emotional responses that income and wealth inequality elicit. Feelings of indifference would be associated with lower redistributive preferences, while sadness, anger, moral outrage, frustration, and compassion would be related to greater support for redistributive policies.

Methods

Data Sources and Sampling

The research was conducted through an online survey administered to representative samples of adults aged 18 and over in Great Britain (n = 3,002) and France (n = 3,012). To ensure representativeness, quotas were applied based on age, gender, and region in both countries, with the French sample also including additional quotas by socio-professional category and size of agglomeration. Data collection took place in June and July 2024. Quality control procedures were implemented to avoid duplicate entries and to identify and remove participants who completed the survey in less than 25% of the median interview duration. An attention-check item was included to ensure the respondent's focus. Before the full rollout, a soft launch was

conducted to test the survey platform and confirm the proper functioning of all filters. The hypotheses guiding the study were preregistered before data collection.¹

The final online survey questionnaire was divided into two main parts: a core section, completed by all respondents and accounting for approximately 70% of the survey, and a modular section, which made up the remaining 30%. In the modular portion, participants were randomly assigned to one of four distinct modules (A, B, C, D), each presenting different stimuli related to economic inequality to assess emotional responses (income inequality, wealth inequality, poor people, and rich people). A minimum of 750 respondents per country completed each module, thereby maintaining representativeness.

Descriptives of sociodemographic variables

The final sample in Britain consisted of 3,002 participants. The mean age was 48.74 years (SD = 17.89), ranging from 18 to 94 years. The average years of education was 14.71 (SD = 4.44), with a range from 1 to 40 years. Regarding gender, 51.8% of participants identified as male (n = 1,556), 47.9% as female (n = 1,438), 0.2% as other (n = 7), and 0.0% (n = 1) reported being unable to choose. See supplementary material for information on sample characterization according to place of residence, household income and subjective social status (Table A, B and C).

In France, the sample included a total of 3,012 participants. The mean age was 49.54 years (SD = 17.41), with participants ranging in age from 18 to 93 years. The average number of years of education completed was 14.53 (SD = 4.31), with a range from 1 to 44 years. In terms of gender, 47.6% of respondents identified as male (n = 1,434), 52.3% as female (n = 1,574), and 0.1% as another gender (n = 4). See supplementary material for information on sample characterization according to place of residence, household income and subjective social status (Table D, E and F).

Operationalisation of key variables

Contact with the rich and the poor. This variable was assessed using two items designed to capture the frequency of everyday encounters with individuals perceived as either much poorer or much richer than the respondent. Participants were asked: *“How often do you have any contact with people who are a lot poorer than you when you are out and about? This might be in the street, on public transport, in shops, in your neighbourhood, or at your workplace.”* and *“How often do you have any contact with people who are a lot richer than you when you are out and about? This might be in the street, on public transport, in shops, in your neighbourhood, or at your workplace.”* For both questions, contact was defined as any interaction—verbal or non-verbal—while “out and about” referred to being in public spaces outside the home, and “neighbourhood” was understood as the local area. Responses were given on a 7-point scale: 1 = Never, 2 = Less than once a month, 3 = Once a month, 4 = Several times a month, 5 = Once a week, 6 = Several times a week, 7 = Every day. An additional option, “Can’t choose”, was available to respondents.

Emotions. Before the main study presented in this paper, the research underwent two preparatory phases to determine the set of emotions to be included in the survey (for more details, see Bastias & Zmerli, under review). As a first phase, online focus groups were conducted in France, Great Britain, and Sweden between December 2021 and February 2022. These sessions, involving 145 participants across 24 groups, explored emotional responses to inequality through moderated discussions and a short follow-up questionnaire assessing reactions to different inequality-related stimuli. Fourteen emotions were initially identified, with additional ones (disgust, admiration, and moral outrage) later incorporated based on team reflection and prior literature. A second phase followed in May 2024 with an online pre-test

¹ <https://aspredicted.org/5ndg-m8xz.pdf> & <https://aspredicted.org/tsmx-dp6q.pdf>

involving 300 respondents per country². The questionnaire of the pre-test was divided into two modules: one used a closed-ended question format, and the other allowed for open responses. Based on the frequency of responses, patterns of co-occurrences (using Chi-square analysis), and the emergence of positive emotions in open answers, the final set of eight emotions selected for the representative survey included: sadness, frustration, admiration, moral outrage, anger, indifference, compassion, and contentment. In the main data collection, participants were then asked to rate the intensity of these eight specific emotions in response to six distinct inequality-related stimuli: income inequality, wealth inequality, poor people, and rich people. The survey prompt read: "When you think about [stimulus] in [country], to what extent do you feel the following emotions?" Responses were recorded on a 5-point scale, ranging from 1 ("not at all") to 5 ("extremely"). An additional option, "Can't choose", was available to respondents. Importantly, respondents were required to assess all eight emotions for each stimulus, with no option to select only a subset.

Redistributive Preferences. This variable was measured using a single-item scale capturing respondents' general position on the trade-off between taxation and government spending on social benefits and services. The wording of the question was: "*There are a number of opposite views on the issue of taxes and social spending. How would you place your views on this scale from 0 to 10?*" Responses were given on a horizontal 11-point scale ranging from 0 to 10, where the endpoints were defined as follows: 0 = 'Government should decrease taxes a lot and spend much less on social benefits and services' and 10 = 'Government should increase taxes a lot and spend much more on social benefits and services'. The scale was visually presented as a horizontal scale with the two opposing statements placed at either end, and an additional "Can't choose" option was also available to participants.

Sociodemographic variables. All regression models controlled for age, gender, household income, subjective social status, and educational attainment.³

Analytical Strategy

First, we assessed how the frequency of interpersonal contact with individuals who were perceived to be poorer or richer than the respondents influenced their redistributive preferences. To do so, we estimated ordinary least squares (OLS) regression models. In this regression, a control variable was included to control for the priming effect that could be exerted by first either presenting emotions towards income inequality (modules A & B) or emotions towards wealth inequality in the questionnaire (modules C & D).

In a second step, we tested whether emotions mediated the effect of contact with poorer individuals on redistributive preferences. We estimated a parallel multiple mediation model (PMMM) using PROCESS Model 4 in SPSS, with 5,000 bootstrap samples (Hayes, 2017) separately for the British and French samples. This approach allowed us to estimate both total and specific indirect effects, as well as direct effects, controlling for the same covariates as in the previous models. In these models, contact with poorer and richer people were the predictors, redistributive preferences was the outcome variable, and eight emotions elicited by income or wealth inequality (sadness, frustration, admiration, moral outrage, anger, indifference, compassion, and contentment) served as mediators. Considering that we conducted analyses with samples from two countries, tested contact with richer and poorer people, and emotions towards income and wealth inequality, we ran, in total, eight parallel multiple mediation models.

² Swedish data was not yet available at the time of the analysis. Only France and Great Britain were included in both the pre-test and the main data collection of this study.

³ See appendix for further information.

Results

Descriptive statistics revealed cross-national differences in key variables (for more detail, see Table G, H, and I). Redistributive preferences were higher in the Britain ($M = 5.29$, $SD = 2.50$) than in France ($M = 4.35$, $SD = 2.42$), with statistically significant differences, while SDO showed comparable averages in both countries, with no statistically significant difference (in France, $M = 3.60$, $SD = 1.76$; in Britain, $M = 3.51$, $SD = 1.82$). British participants also reported slightly more frequent contact with both poorer ($M = 4.24$, $SD = 1.92$) and richer individuals ($M = 3.79$, $SD = 1.91$) compared to their French counterparts ($M = 4.16$, $SD = 1.93$ and $M = 3.54$, $SD = 1.90$, respectively). While the difference in contact with poorer individuals was not significant ($t(5533) = 1.51$, $p = .131$, $\Delta M = 0.08$), contact with richer individuals was.

Figure 1

Means of emotions towards income and wealth inequality

As illustrated in Figure 1, regarding the emotional responses, participants reported moderate levels of moral outrage, anger, sadness, compassion, and frustration in response to both income and wealth inequality⁴. Admiration, indifference, and contentment were generally low across both countries. We also observed differences in emotional responses across the two types of inequality and between countries. Overall, income inequality elicited stronger emotional reactions than wealth inequality, especially in terms of compassion among British participants and frustration in both countries. On the other hand, emotional responses varied significantly between countries, French respondents were especially likely to express moral outrage and anger—particularly in response to income inequality—while compassion was more prominent among British participants⁵.

⁴ Emotions about the other four stimuli (poor people and rich people) are reported in Figure A in supplementary materials.

⁵ Sadness was the only emotion that showed no significant difference between the two samples for either income inequality ($t(2885) = 0.62$, $p = .536$) or wealth inequality ($t(2886) = 0.75$, $p = .454$).

Figure 2

Effect of contact with poor and rich people on redistributive preferences

Note. Age, gender, household income, education, and subjective social status included as control variables along with income/wealth prime.

Effects of Contact with Poorer People

PMMM were estimated separately for the British and French samples. The first models tested frequency of contact with much poorer people as the predictor, redistributive preferences as the outcome variable, and eight emotions elicited by *income inequality* as mediators (see Figure 3). All models included relevant covariates and confidence intervals for indirect effects were estimated using 5,000 bootstrap samples and the following control variables: Age, gender, household income, education, and subjective social status.

Figure 3

Mediators: Emotions elicited by income inequality

Britain

France

As shown in Figure 3, the results for the British sample (N = 1,090) indicated that the model explained 17.6% of the variance in redistributive preferences ($R^2 = 0.176$, $MSE = 5.35$, $F(14, 1075) = 16.35$, $p < .001$). Although the total effect was significant ($B = .16$, $p = .046$), the direct effect was not ($B = -.03$, $p = .67$), suggesting a full mediation effect. The total indirect effect was significant ($B = .19$, 95% CI [.12, .27]), with several specific emotional mediators—sadness, moral outrage, anger, and compassion.

For France (N = 1,077), the model explained 11.9% of the variance in redistributive preferences ($R^2 = 0.119$, $MSE = 5.38$, $F(14, 1062) = 10.27$, $p < .001$). The total effect of contact with poorer people on redistributive preferences was significant ($B = .28$, $p = .0002$), and, in contrast to the British sample, the direct effect remained significant even after accounting for mediators ($B = .22$, $p = .003$), suggesting partial mediation. The total indirect effect was smaller but significant ($B = .06$, 95% CI [.01, .11]) and among the emotional mediators, only sadness and moral outrage exhibited indirect effects.

These findings suggest that, in both countries, the relationship between contacts with poorer people and redistributive preferences is at least partially explained by emotional responses to inequality—particularly sadness and moral outrage—which served as significant mediators in both samples, highlighting the central role of these emotions in linking interpersonal contact with support for redistribution.

Figure 4

Mediators: Emotions elicited by wealth inequality

Britain

France

As presented in Figure 4, in Britain (N = 1,087), when it comes to emotions towards wealth inequality as mediators of the effect of contact with poorer people on redistributive preferences, the model explained 13.7% of the variance ($R^2 = 0.137$, $MSE = 5.33$, $F(14, 1072) = 12.14$, $p < .001$). The total effect of contact with poorer people on redistributive preferences was significant ($B = .38$, $p < .001$), and the direct effect remained significant even after accounting for the mediators ($B = .24$, $p = .001$), indicating partial mediation. The total indirect effect was

also significant ($B = .14$, 95% CI [.08, .20]), with specific emotions—moral outrage, indifference and compassion— emerging as significant mediators of the relationship.

In France ($N = 1,069$), the model explained 13.6% of the variance in redistributive preferences ($R^2 = 0.136$, $MSE = 5.14$, $F(14, 1054) = 11.87$, $p < .001$). The total effect was significant ($B = .20$, $p = .009$), while the direct effect was not ($B = .10$, $p = .17$), suggesting that the relationship was fully mediated by the included emotions (indirect effect was $B = .10$, 95% CI [.05, .15]). As in the British case, moral outrage and indifference showed significant indirect effects.

Figure 5

Mediators: Emotions elicited by representations of poor people

Britain

France

In the British sample, contact with poorer people significantly predicted greater redistributive preferences (total effect $B = 0.37$, $p < .001$), even after accounting for mediators (direct effect $B = 0.24$, $p = .001$), indicating partial mediation (see Figure 5). The total indirect effect was significant ($B = 0.13$, 95% CI [0.07, 0.19]); specifically, moral outrage, indifference, and compassion acted as significant mediators. In France, contact with poorer people was also associated with greater redistributive preferences (total effect $B = 0.20$, $p = .008$), but this effect was no longer significant when emotions elicited by thinking of the poor were included as mediators (direct effect $B = 0.09$, $p = .215$), indicating full mediation. The total indirect effect was significant ($B = 0.11$, 95% CI [0.05, 0.17]); specifically, moral outrage and indifference were significant mediators.

Figure 6

Mediators: Emotions elicited by representations of rich people

Britain

France

As displayed in Figure 6, in the British sample, contact with poorer people was a significant predictor of greater redistributive preferences (total effect $B = 0.35$, $p < .001$), and this association persisted after controlling for emotions towards the rich (direct effect $B = 0.31$, $p < .001$), showing that the relationship is direct without indirect effect ($B = 0.04$, 95% CI [-0.003, 0.09]). However, moral outrage ($B = 0.024$, 95% CI [0.001, 0.058]) emerged as a small yet statistically meaningful mediator. Likewise, among the French participants, contact with poorer people also predicted higher support for redistribution (total effect $B = 0.19$, $p = .012$), even after controlling the mediators (direct effect $B = 0.15$, $p = .043$). The effect was only direct, since total indirect effect was not statistically significant ($B = 0.04$, 95% CI [-0.01, 0.10]). Notably, as well as in Britain, moral outrage towards the rich plays a role in linking contact with poorer people to support for redistribution; however, in France, compassion with the rich acted as a negative mediator.

Effects of Contact with Richer People

Figure 7

Mediators: Emotions elicited by income inequality

Britain

In the British sample (N = 1,084), the frequency of contact with richer people as the predictor showed that the model explained 17.3% of the variance in redistributive preferences ($R^2 = 0.173$, $MSE = 5.40$, $F(14, 1069) = 16.01$, $p < .001$). Figure 7 shows that while the total effect of contact with richer people on redistributive preferences was significant ($B = .16$, $p = .043$), the direct effect was not ($B = .07$, $p = .34$), suggesting a fully mediated association through compassion and admiration. The total indirect effect was $B = .09$, 95% CI [0.02, 0.16]). In the French case (N = 1,082) the model explained 11.2% of the variance in redistributive preferences ($R^2 = 0.112$, $MSE = 5.48$, $F(14, 1067) = 9.60$, $p < .001$). However, neither the total effect ($B = .04$, $p = .59$) nor the direct effect ($B = .01$, $p = .89$) and the total indirect reached statistical significance ($B = .03$, 95% CI [-0.02, .08]).

When analysing emotions elicited by wealth inequality, contact with richer people was not associated —neither directly nor indirectly through emotions—with support for redistribution. These results are shown in the supplementary material (see Figure B).

Figure 8

Mediators: Emotions elicited by representations of rich people

Britain

France

Across both countries, as shown in Figure 8, contact with rich people does not reliably predict support for redistribution through emotions toward the rich. In Britain, the association is only direct ($B = .22, p = .006$) and remains also significant after accounting for the mediators ($B = .24, p = .002$), while in France, no significant direct or indirect association was found. In the British case, although admiration showed significant associations with both contact and redistributive preferences, its specific indirect effect was not statistically significant ($B = -0.018, \text{BootCI} [-0.045, 0.001]$).

Figure 9

Mediators: Emotions elicited by representations of poor people

Britain

France

Similarly, contact with richer people does not predict support for redistribution through emotions elicited by representations of the poor, in both countries (see Figure 9). In France, no direct or indirect effects were detected. In Britain, the total indirect effect is not statistically significant, while there is a total direct effect ($B = 0.27, p < .001$), which remains significant after controlling for the mediators ($B = 0.22, p = .003$). Serving as a small but significant mediator, only compassion showed a significant specific indirect effect ($B = 0.019, 95\% \text{ CI} [0.001, 0.047]$). To sum up, across both countries, contact with the rich does not lead to greater support for redistribution via emotional responses—whether toward rich or poor people. In Britain, the relationship is direct, while in France, no significant direct or indirect effects were observed.

DISCUSSION

A person's perception of inequality within their society stems from social comparisons (Dawtry et al., 2015, 2019). However, individuals do not seem to compare their socioeconomic situation with the wealthiest members of society, but rather in comparison to those around them in their

everyday environment (Lazarsfeld & Merton, 1954; Marsden, 1987; McPherson, Smith-Lovin & Cook, 2001; Reagans, 2011). When special and social segregation are present, substantial inequalities are not evident at the local level, and the sense of urgency for redistribution may decrease (Bailey, 2013; Kadt, 2020; Newman, 2014; Vargas Salfate & Stern, 2023; Vázquez et al., 2022). Thus, the individuals one interacts with can play a crucial role in shaping perceptions of inequality and, consequently, impact political attitudes and behaviours.

Building on these ideas, we ground this work in the belief that redistributive preferences are strongly shaped by individuals' social interactions. Exposure to poorer or richer individuals, in this setting, may serve as a reference point for perceiving societal inequality and motivating efforts to reduce it. We acknowledge that the literature still lacks a clear differentiation of the mechanisms through which class-based context shapes political behaviour (Nathan & Sands, 2023). Addressing this gap can contribute to more robust theoretical development and allow for a better assessment of external validity across different settings. In this study, we focus on emotions as a key psychological mechanism that may shed light on how inter-class contact can foster support for resource redistribution.

Our findings provide compelling evidence that, in both countries studied, the effect of contact with poorer people on support for redistribution is mediated by specific emotions—moral outrage and sadness elicited by income inequality, and moral outrage and indifference elicited by wealth inequality—with full mediation via emotions about income observed only in Britain, and full mediation via emotions about wealth only in France. In these cases of complete mediation, it is not contact itself, but the specific emotions it arouses that account for increased support for redistributive measures. Additionally, emotions toward the poor (especially moral outrage, compassion, and indifference—negatively related—) and emotions toward the rich (moral outrage in both countries, and compassion only in France) also help explain how contact with poorer people influences redistributive preferences.

Interestingly, unlike interaction with poorer people, contact with richer people has a smaller and null effect on redistribution. In both countries, the direct effect of this type of contact on support for redistribution was not significant. The only exception occurs in Britain, where emotions toward poor people play a role; this is when a direct effect is observed. Regarding indirect effects, the relationship was not mediated by emotions elicited by any of the stimuli (wealth inequality, income inequality, poor people, and rich people), with the sole exception of admiration and compassion toward income inequality, which played a mediating role exclusively in the British context. In the case of admiration and compassion, they tend to be emotions directed toward people rather than situations. Therefore, despite having been asked about income inequality, respondents may have had the economically advantaged or disadvantaged person in mind when answering⁶.

Overall, analyses provided a comprehensive test of the hypothesis that social contact influences attitudes toward redistribution both directly and indirectly, through the emotional responses that different types of representations of economic inequality elicit. However, this pattern holds primarily when contact occurs with poorer individuals, confirming H1. Conversely, we reject H2, as frequent contact with richer individuals did not correlate with negative emotions toward income or wealth inequality. As for H3, we partially confirm this hypothesis, since we expected that social contact with poor as well as with rich individuals would influence attitudes toward

⁶ Judging by the positive association between redistribution and both admiration and compassion, we believe it may have been the economically disadvantaged person. Furthermore, further support of this assumption is found in the model contact with richer people-emotions toward the rich-redistribution. Here, contact with the rich increases admiration (toward them), and this, in turn, is negative associated to redistributive preferences.

redistribution via emotional responses to income and wealth inequality. This was not observed for contact with richer people, except for the mediating role of admiration and compassion toward income inequality in Britain.

Among the mediating emotions, feelings of indifference toward wealth inequality and poor people—unlike the other inequality-related stimuli—mediate the relationship between contact with poorer people and support for redistribution in both countries. In this case, higher levels of indifference are associated with lower support for redistributive policies. Other emotions like sadness (towards income inequality) and compassion (towards poor people and, only in France, towards the rich) show relative relevance as mediators targeting specific inequality-related stimuli. Anger and frustration, however, do not appear to play a significant role in redistributive policies in our study. Nevertheless, moral outrage elicited by any of the four stimuli presented (income inequality, wealth inequality, poor people, and rich people) emerged, among the eight tested emotions, as the only one that appears robustly mediated in the relationship between contact with poorer people and redistributive preferences. This finding underscores the central and consistent role of moral outrage as a key emotional pathway through which class-based contact translates into greater support for redistributive policies. All in all, these results are consistent with previous research that has found that emotions play a critical role in shaping people's support for policies that address economic inequality or seek to reduce poverty (Thomas & McGarty, 2011; Krauth-Guber & Bonnot, 2020; Landmann & Hess 2016; Hechler & Kessler, 2018; Harth, Kessler & Leach, 2008; Tan, Liu, Zheng & Huang, 2015; Luengo Kanacri et al. 2016). Specifically, it enriches the literature on moral outrage (Garcia-Castro et al., 2022; Montada & Schneider, 1989; Vezzoli et al., 2022; Wakslak, Jost, Tyler & Chen, 2007). We expect that insight from this work helps to advance our understanding of the psychological mechanisms underlying attitude change and to underscore the value of targeting emotional processes in efforts to foster social and political change.

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Supplementary Materials

Table A

British sample characterized by Place of Residence

Place of residence	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
East Midlands	218	7.3	7.3
East of England	263	8.8	8.8
London	415	13.8	13.8
North East	119	4	4
North West	351	11.7	11.7
Scotland	258	8.6	8.6
South East	433	14.4	14.4
South West	277	9.2	9.2
Wales	146	4.9	4.9
West Midlands	266	8.9	8.9
Yorkshire and The Humber	253	8.4	8.4
Total	2999	99.9	100
Missing: System	3	0.1	
Grand Total	3002	100	

Table B

British sample characterized by Household income

Household income	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
A. Less than £1,014	216	7.2	7.7
B. £1,014 to under £1,409	263	8.8	9.3
C. £1,409 to under £1,790	257	8.6	9.1
D. £1,790 to under £2,190	297	9.9	10.5
E. £2,190 to under £2,659	356	11.9	12.6
F. £2,659 to under £3,162	302	10.1	10.7
G. £3,162 to under £3,799	324	10.8	11.5
H. £3,799 to under £4,617	322	10.7	11.4
I. £4,617 to under £6,063	237	7.9	8.4
J. £6,063 or more	245	8.2	8.7
Total	2819	93.9	100
Missing: System	183	6.1	
Grand Total	3002	100	

Table C

British sample characterized by Subjective Social Status

Subjective Social status	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
1 Bottom	60	2	2.1
2	84	2.8	3
3	238	7.9	8.4
4	391	13	13.8
5	710	23.7	25
6	600	20	21.1
7	450	15	15.9
8	208	6.9	7.3
9	47	1.6	1.7
10 Top	51	1.7	1.8
Total	2839	94.6	100
Missing: System	163	5.4	
Grand Total	3002	100	

Table D

French sample characterized by Place of Residence

Place of residence	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
Auvergne - Rhône-Alpes	370	12.3	12.3
Bourgogne - Franche-Comté	127	4.2	4.2
Bretagne	157	5.2	5.2
Centre - Val de Loire	120	4	4
Grand Est	259	8.6	8.6
Hauts-de-France	274	9.1	9.1
Île de France	556	18.5	18.5
Normandie	149	4.9	5
Nouvelle Aquitaine	291	9.7	9.7
Occitanie	287	9.5	9.6
Pays-de-la-Loire	179	5.9	6
Provence-Alpes-Côte d'Azur	232	7.7	7.7
Total	3001	99.6	100
Missing: System	11	0.4	
Grand Total	3012	100	

Table E

French sample characterized by Household Income

Household Income	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
A. Less than 1,000 euros	152	5	5.4
B. From 1,000 to 1,500 euros	262	8.7	9.4
C. From 1,501 to 1,700 euros	166	5.5	5.9
D. From 1,701 to 2,000 euros	240	8	8.6
E. From 2,001 to 2,300 euros	250	8.3	8.9
F. From 2,301 to 2,600 euros	208	6.9	7.4
G. From 2,601 to 3,000 euros	258	8.6	9.2
H. From 3,001 to 3,300 euros	257	8.5	9.2
I. From 3,301 to 4,000 euros	416	13.8	14.8
J. More than 4,000 euros	593	19.7	21.2
Total	2802	93	100
Missing: System	210	7	
Grand Total	3012	100	

Table F

French sample characterized by Subjective Social status

Subjective Social status	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
1 (Bottom)	111	3.7	3.8
2	124	4.1	4.3
3	328	10.9	11.3
4	419	13.9	14.4
5	829	27.5	28.5
6	596	19.8	20.5
7	337	11.2	11.6
8	118	3.9	4.1
9	25	0.8	0.9
10 (Top)	21	0.7	0.7
Total	2908	96.5	100
Missing: System	104	3.5	
Grand Total	3012	100	

Table G

Descriptive Statistics for Redistributive Preferences (scale 0-10)

Country	N	Min	Max	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>
Britain	2843	0	10	5.29	2.502
France	2866	0	10	4.35	2.419

Table H

Descriptive Statistics for contact with poorer people

Country	Category	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
Britain	Never	251	8.4	9.1
	Less than once a month	482	16.1	17.5
	Once a month	193	6.4	7
	Several times a month	622	20.7	22.6
	Once a week	224	7.5	8.1
	Several times a week	623	20.8	22.6
	Every day	363	12.1	13.2
	Valid total	2758	91.9	100
	Missing (system)	244	8.1	
	Total	3002	100	
France	Never	264	8.8	9.5
	Less than once a month	494	16.4	17.8
	Once a month	224	7.4	8.1
	Several times a month	670	22.2	24.1
	Once a week	184	6.1	6.6
	Several times a week	567	18.8	20.4
	Every day	374	12.4	13.5
	Valid total	2777	92.2	100
	Missing (system)	235	7.8	
	Total	3012	100	

Table I

Descriptive Statistics for contact with richer people

Country	Category	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
Britain	Never	348	11.6	12.7
	Less than once a month	588	19.6	21.5
	Once a month	280	9.3	10.2
	Several times a month	589	19.6	21.5
	Once a week	209	7	7.6
	Several times a week	472	15.7	17.2
	Every day	255	8.5	9.3
	Valid total	2741	91.3	100
	Missing (system)	261	8.7	
	Total	3002	100	
France	Never	447	14.8	16.1
	Less than once a month	626	20.8	22.5
	Once a month	307	10.2	11

Several times a month	655	21.7	23.5
Once a week	125	4.2	4.5
Several times a week	380	12.6	13.6
Every day	245	8.1	8.8
Valid total	2785	92.5	100
Missing (system)	227	7.5	
Total	3012	100	

Figure A

Mediators: Emotions elicited by wealth inequality

Britain

France

The results of the PMMM conducted on the British sample (N = 1,081) with contact with richer people as the predictor and emotions towards wealth inequality as mediators showed that the model explained 13.4% of the variance in redistributive preferences ($R^2 = 0.134$, $MSE = 5.34$, $F(14, 1066) = 11.75$, $p < .001$). The total effect of contact with richer people on redistributive preferences was significant ($B = .17$, $p = .033$), whereas the direct effect ($B = .13$, $p = .074$) and the total indirect effect ($B = .03$, 95% CI [-0.02, .09]) were not statistically significant. In the French sample (N = 1,064), the model explained 13.1% of the variance in redistributive preferences ($R^2 = 0.131$, $MSE = 5.18$, $F(14, 1049) = 11.25$, $p < .001$). In this case, neither the total effect ($B = .05$, $p = .55$) nor the direct effect ($B = .04$, $p = .54$) nor the total indirect effect were significant ($B = .002$, 95% CI [-0.05, .05]).